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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL SAMAN P.I** bearing USN **2017BCAAM001** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHILASH MESTHA** bearing USN **2017BCAAM002** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHWATHI-T** bearing USN **2017BCAAM003** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHWIN K** bearing USN **2017BCAAM004** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOYAL DSILVA** bearing USN **2017BCAAM005** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MEGHANA U BYNDOOR** bearing USN **2017BCAAM006** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MAZHAR K.A** bearing USN **2017BCAAM007** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOKSHITH** bearing USN **2017BCAAM008** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIHAL ISMAIL E.P** bearing USN **2017BCAAM009** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **OMKARADITHYA** bearing USN **2017BCAAM010** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREELAKSHMI.A** bearing USN **2017BCAAM011** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUDARSHAN B J** bearing USN **2017BCAAM012** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHNAV B** bearing USN **2017BCAAM013** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKIL A** bearing USN **2017BCACC001** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AVIN V BANGERA** bearing USN **2017BCACC002** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHAN CH** bearing USN **2017BCACC003** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD ARAFAZ DK** bearing USN **2017BCACC004** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASAD** bearing USN **2017BCACC005** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **P.SHIVA RAM KUMAR** bearing USN **2017BCACC008** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAJWAL** bearing USN **2017BCACC009** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAMEEJ PM** bearing USN **2017BCACC010** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAILESH.S** bearing USN **2017BCACC011** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEHARI T** bearing USN **2017BCACC012** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VICHITH CHANDRAN** bearing USN **2017BCACC013** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH KANA** bearing USN **2017BCASD001** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHILA P M** bearing USN **2017BCASD002** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMOOLYA AR** bearing USN **2017BCASD003** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARATHI RAJAGOPALAN** bearing USN **2017BCASD004** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARVIND SINGH RAO** bearing USN **2017BCASD005** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AYSHATHUL BAREERA** bearing USN **2017BCASD006** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DRAVYAPRABHA.V** bearing USN **2017BCASD007** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IMZAM K.A** bearing USN **2017BCASD008** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JEVIAN LOY DSOUZA** bearing USN **2017BCASD009** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K SIDHARTH RAMDAS** bearing USN **2017BCASD010** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA RAJAN PV** bearing USN **2017BCASD011** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHSHOOQUE** bearing USN **2017BCASD012** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS P.A** bearing USN **2017BCASD013** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MIQDHAD CP** bearing USN **2017BCASD014** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SAFWAN RAHEEM** bearing USN **2017BCASD015** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDINI M** bearing USN **2017BCASD016** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAJWAL** bearing USN **2017BCASD017** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAKYATHJI KOTIAN** bearing USN **2017BCASD018** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDHYA** bearing USN **2017BCASD019** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SARISHMA.V** bearing USN **2017BCASD020** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYYED RIZWAN** bearing USN **2017BCASD021** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHABAAZ** bearing USN **2017BCASD022** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAM M JAMES** bearing USN **2017BCASD023** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIFANA** bearing USN **2017BCASD024** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUHAIB SK** bearing USN **2017BCASD025** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2017**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SURAYYA** bearing USN **2017BCASD026** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2017**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THASREENA BANU** bearing USN **2017BCASD027** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHAK NAIR C** bearing USN **2017BCASD028** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHANDAN GANGADHAR TANDEL** bearing USN **2017BCASD029** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIHAL ISMAIL E.P** bearing USN **2017BCAAM009** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **OMKARADITHYA** bearing USN **2017BCAAM010** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREELAKSHMI.A** bearing USN **2017BCAAM011** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHNAV B** bearing USN **2017BCAAM013** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKIL A** bearing USN **2017BCACC001** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AVIN V BANGERA** bearing USN **2017BCACC002** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD ARAZ DK** bearing USN **2017BCACC004** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASAD** bearing USN **2017BCACC005** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SAWAF** bearing USN **2017BCACC006** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **P.SHIVA RAM KUMAR** bearing USN **2017BCACC008** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAMEEJ PM** bearing USN **2017BCACC010** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAILESH.S** bearing USN **2017BCACC011** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VICHITH CHANDRAN** bearing USN **2017BCACC013** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH KANA** bearing USN **2017BCASD001** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHILA P M** bearing USN **2017BCASD002** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMOOLYA AR** bearing USN **2017BCASD003** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARATHI RAJAGOPALAN** bearing USN **2017BCASD004** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARVIND SINGH RAO** bearing USN **2017BCASD005** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AYSHATHUL BAREERA** bearing USN **2017BCASD006** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DRAVYAPRABHA.V** bearing USN **2017BCASD007** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IMZAM K.A** bearing USN **2017BCASD008** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JEVIAN LOY DSOUZA** bearing USN **2017BCASD009** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K SIDHARTH RAMDAS** bearing USN **2017BCASD010** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA RAJAN PV** bearing USN **2017BCASD011** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHSHOOQUE** bearing USN **2017BCASD012** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS P.A** bearing USN **2017BCASD013** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MIQDHAD CP** bearing USN **2017BCASD014** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SAFWAN RAHEEM** bearing USN **2017BCASD015** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDINI M** bearing USN **2017BCASD016** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAKYATHJI KOTIAN** bearing USN **2017BCASD018** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDHYA** bearing USN **2017BCASD019** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SARISHMA.V** bearing USN **2017BCASD020** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYYED RIZWAN** bearing USN **2017BCASD021** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHABAAZ** bearing USN **2017BCASD022** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAM M JAMES** bearing USN **2017BCASD023** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIFANA** bearing USN **2017BCASD024** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2017**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUHAIB SK** bearing USN **2017BCASD025** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SURAYYA** bearing USN **2017BCASD026** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THASREENA BANU** bearing USN **2017BCASD027** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHAK NAIR C** bearing USN **2017BCASD028** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2017**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHANDAN GANGADHAR TANDEL** bearing USN **2017BCASD029** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the II SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2017.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL SAMAN P.I** bearing USN **2017BCAAM001** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHILASH MESTHA** bearing USN **2017BCAAM002** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOYAL DSILVA** bearing USN **2017BCAAM005** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MEGHANA U BYNDOOR** bearing USN **2017BCAAM006** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MAZHAR K.A** bearing USN **2017BCAAM007** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD ARAFAZ DK** bearing USN **2017BCACC004** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASAD** bearing USN **2017BCACC005** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SAWAF** bearing USN **2017BCACC006** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUSTHAFA G TORGAL** bearing USN **2017BCACC007** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **P.SHIVA RAM KUMAR** bearing USN **2017BCACC008** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAJWAL** bearing USN **2017BCACC009** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAMEEJ PM** bearing USN **2017BCACC010** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAILESH.S** bearing USN **2017BCACC011** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEHARI T** bearing USN **2017BCACC012** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VICHITH CHANDRAN** bearing USN **2017BCACC013** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH KANA** bearing USN **2017BCASD001** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHILA P M** bearing USN **2017BCASD002** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMOOLYA AR** bearing USN **2017BCASD003** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARATHI RAJAGOPALAN** bearing USN **2017BCASD004** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARVIND SINGH RAO** bearing USN **2017BCASD005** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AYSHATHUL BAREERA** bearing USN **2017BCASD006** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DRAVYAPRABHA.V** bearing USN **2017BCASD007** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JEVIAN LOY DSOUZA** bearing USN **2017BCASD009** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K SIDHARTH RAMDAS** bearing USN **2017BCASD010** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA RAJAN PV** bearing USN **2017BCASD011** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHSHOOQUE** bearing USN **2017BCASD012** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS P.A** bearing USN **2017BCASD013** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MIQDHAD CP** bearing USN **2017BCASD014** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SAFWAN RAHEEM** bearing USN **2017BCASD015** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDINI M** bearing USN **2017BCASD016** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAJWAL** bearing USN **2017BCASD017** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAKYATHJI KOTIAN** bearing USN **2017BCASD018** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDHYA** bearing USN **2017BCASD019** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SARISHMA.V** bearing USN **2017BCASD020** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYYED RIZWAN** bearing USN **2017BCASD021** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHABAAZ** bearing USN **2017BCASD022** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAM M JAMES** bearing USN **2017BCASD023** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIFANA** bearing USN **2017BCASD024** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUHAIB SK** bearing USN **2017BCASD025** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SURAYYA** bearing USN **2017BCASD026** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THASREENA BANU** bearing USN **2017BCASD027** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHAK NAIR C** bearing USN **2017BCASD028** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHANDAN GANGADHAR TANDEL** bearing USN **2017BCASD029** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL SAMAN P.I** bearing USN **2017BCAAM001** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHILASH MESTHA** bearing USN **2017BCAAM002** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHWATHI-T** bearing USN **2017BCAAM003** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHWIN K** bearing USN **2017BCAAM004** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOYAL DSILVA** bearing USN **2017BCAAM005** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MEGHANA U BYNDOOR** bearing USN **2017BCAAM006** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MAZHAR K.A** bearing USN **2017BCAAM007** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the IV SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOKSHITH** bearing USN **2017BCAAM008** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIHAL ISMAIL E.P** bearing USN **2017BCAAM009** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **OMKARADITHYA** bearing USN **2017BCAAM010** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREELAKSHMI.A** bearing USN **2017BCAAM011** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUDARSHAN B J** bearing USN **2017BCAAM012** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHNAV B** bearing USN **2017BCAAM013** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKIL A** bearing USN **2017BCACC001** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AVIN V BANGERA** bearing USN **2017BCACC002** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEHARI T** bearing USN **2017BCACC012** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VICHITH CHANDRAN** bearing USN **2017BCACC013** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH KANA** bearing USN **2017BCASD001** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKHILA P M** bearing USN **2017BCASD002** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMOOLYA AR** bearing USN **2017BCASD003** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARATHI RAJAGOPALAN** bearing USN **2017BCASD004** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARVIND SINGH RAO** bearing USN **2017BCASD005** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AYSHATHUL BAREERA** bearing USN **2017BCASD006** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DRAVYAPRABHA.V** bearing USN **2017BCASD007** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IMZAM K.A** bearing USN **2017BCASD008** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JEVIAN LOY DSOUZA** bearing USN **2017BCASD009** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K SIDHARTH RAMDAS** bearing USN **2017BCASD010** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA RAJAN PV** bearing USN **2017BCASD011** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHSHOOQUE** bearing USN **2017BCASD012** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS P.A** bearing USN **2017BCASD013** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MIQDHAD CP** bearing USN **2017BCASD014** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the IV SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SAFWAN RAHEEM** bearing USN **2017BCASD015** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the IV SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDINI M** bearing USN **2017BCASD016** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAJWAL** bearing USN **2017BCASD017** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAKYATHJI KOTIAN** bearing USN **2017BCASD018** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDHYA** bearing USN **2017BCASD019** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SARISHMA.V** bearing USN **2017BCASD020** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYYED RIZWAN** bearing USN **2017BCASD021** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHABAAZ** bearing USN **2017BCASD022** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAM M JAMES** bearing USN **2017BCASD023** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIFANA** bearing USN **2017BCASD024** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUHAIB SK** bearing USN **2017BCASD025** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SURAYYA** bearing USN **2017BCASD026** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THASREENA BANU** bearing USN **2017BCASD027** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHAK NAIR C** bearing USN **2017BCASD028** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2018**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHANDAN GANGADHAR TANDEL** bearing USN **2017BCASD029** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the IV SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2018.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL SAMAN P.I** bearing USN **2017BCAAM001** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHILASH MESTHA** bearing USN **2017BCAAM002** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHWATHI-T** bearing USN **2017BCAAM003** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHWIN K** bearing USN **2017BCAAM004** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOYAL DSILVA** bearing USN **2017BCAAM005** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MEGHANA U BYNDOOR** bearing USN **2017BCAAM006** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MAZHAR K.A** bearing USN **2017BCAAM007** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOKSHITH** bearing USN **2017BCAAM008** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIHAL ISMAIL E.P** bearing USN **2017BCAAM009** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **OMKARADITHYA** bearing USN **2017BCAAM010** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREELAKSHMI.A** bearing USN **2017BCAAM011** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUDARSHAN B J** bearing USN **2017BCAAM012** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHNAV B** bearing USN **2017BCAAM013** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKIL A** bearing USN **2017BCACC001** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AVIN V BANGERA** bearing USN **2017BCACC002** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHAN CH** bearing USN **2017BCACC003** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD ARAZ DK** bearing USN **2017BCACC004** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ASAD** bearing USN **2017BCACC005** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD SAWAF** bearing USN **2017BCACC006** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUSTHAFA G TORGAL** bearing USN **2017BCACC007** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **P.SHIVA RAM KUMAR** bearing USN **2017BCACC008** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAJWAL** bearing USN **2017BCACC009** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAMEEJ PM** bearing USN **2017BCACC010** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAILESH.S** bearing USN **2017BCACC011** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VICHITH CHANDRAN** bearing USN **2017BCACC013** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DRAVYAPRABHA.V** bearing USN **2017BCASD007** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **IMZAM K.A** bearing USN **2017BCASD008** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JEVIAN LOY DSOUZA** bearing USN **2017BCASD009** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K SIDHARTH RAMDAS** bearing USN **2017BCASD010** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KEERTHANA RAJAN PV** bearing USN **2017BCASD011** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHSHOOQUE** bearing USN **2017BCASD012** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED ANAS P.A** bearing USN **2017BCASD013** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED MIQDHAD CP** bearing USN **2017BCASD014** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SAFWAN RAHEEM** bearing USN **2017BCASD015** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NANDINI M** bearing USN **2017BCASD016** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAJWAL** bearing USN **2017BCASD017** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAKYATHJI KOTIAN** bearing USN **2017BCASD018** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDHYA** bearing USN **2017BCASD019** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SARISHMA.V** bearing USN **2017BCASD020** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2019.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYYED RIZWAN** bearing USN **2017BCASD021** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHABAAZ** bearing USN **2017BCASD022** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAM M JAMES** bearing USN **2017BCASD023** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIFANA** bearing USN **2017BCASD024** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUHAIB SK** bearing USN **2017BCASD025** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SURAYYA** bearing USN **2017BCASD026** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THASREENA BANU** bearing USN **2017BCASD027** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VAISHAK NAIR C** bearing USN **2017BCASD028** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2019**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHANDAN GANGADHAR TANDEL** bearing USN **2017BCASD029** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2019**.

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